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D6.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA2

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Abbreviations

AHA	Active and Healthy Ageing
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
IEXPAC	Instrument for Evaluation of the Experience of Chronic Patients
IoT	Internet of Things
JRA	Joint Research Activity
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
PCHC	Paretian Classification of Health Change
PEU	Perceived Ease of Use
PU	Perceived Usefulness
PROM	Patient Reported Outcomes Measures
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SD	Standard Deviation
SUS	System Usability Scale
TAM	Technology Acceptance Measurement
UA	User Acceptance
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document describes the activities carried out within the context of JRA2 – Transitional Care, focusing on four case studies: a simulation phase pilot conducted in Finland, and three small-scale pilot studies conducted in Greece, Canada and Spain. It provides a detailed account of each phase and activity undertaken by each case study, including pilot definition, execution phase, evaluation, results and conclusions.

Furthermore, it presents a harmonized analysis across Living Labs in transitional care, addressing aspects such as the services offered by the Living Labs, their utilization in the pilots, and how their use can contribute to such studies. In healthcare innovation, involving Living Lab creates inclusive environments that involves various stakeholders, aligning regulatory standards, clinical protocols, and human factors to develop effective transitional care solutions based on digital solutions. Capacity building initiatives and collaborative sessions engage diverse stakeholders, while simulation tests and real-world experiments refine interventions iteratively, supported by data collection methods to predict outcomes and ensure compliance with legal and safety standards throughout the innovation process.

A comparative analysis has been conducted on the devices used and the data collected by them, as well as the PROMs/PREMs gathered in the context of the JRA2. Additionally, an economic impact assessment has been carried out, evaluating data collection in Living Labs for transitional care and compares home monitoring devices to clinical tools, addressing patient transition challenges. Case studies aim to streamline care and reduce readmission costs through real-time monitoring, offering insights for policymakers to improve EU healthcare systems and lower expenses.

Finally, a series of recommendations regarding practices in Transitional Care are provided: engaging patients and clinicians in the design phase ensures that home monitoring technologies effectively meet real-world needs, while standardized protocols and international pilot studies guarantee data consistency and applicability; thorough training for medical personnel in adopting new technologies is key for their smooth integration into clinical practice; supporting patient recovery with user-friendly interfaces and continuous feedback mechanisms for optimal transitional care management.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of the JRA process

The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) served as a test bed for all the internal harmonisation procedures, for assessing and improving the provided services, as well as the research cases that could be the basis for the external researchers through the transnational and virtual access procedures. Activities focused on three different domains in Living Lab Health & Wellbeing research: rehabilitation (WP5), transitional care (WP6) and everyday living environments (WP7).

In order to harmonise procedures as much as possible, **common JRA stand-up meetings** across WP5-6-7 were organized. During these meetings we exchanged ideas, challenges and improvements for the activities that we performed in the JRAs and the procedures we agreed upon (such as a standard template for scenario, report and data collection methods, as well as recruitment strategy, etc.). After the first intensive phase, these meetings were organised monthly instead of bi-weekly. A Teams folder called *JRAs general channel* was created to share materials and reports. A **common template and scenario** were developed for data collection of the co-creation sessions of phase 1. Moreover, we decided to focus as much as possible on patients with stroke or mild cognitive impairments instead of including all chronic diseases.

To keep track of JRA progression, LiCalab created a **status report** Excel file called **Vitalise overview JRA activities** in which each partner regularly reported the status of his case study (preparation, deployment phase, running phase). The preparation phase showed the participants' sample size and profile as well as the status of ethical approval. In the deployment phase we determined how many participants were contacted, screened and recruited what the status of the information sessions was and, if applicable, whether technology was deployed. The running phase provided an overview of the data collection from pre, intermediary, and post measurements as well as data collection from devices, applications and software. Finally, the number of participants that completed the study was mentioned. Another tab in the file was meant to report discussions on challenges, actions required to resolve those, and lessons learned

1.2 Description of JRA2 – Transitional Care

The JRA2 for transitional care studies the transit needs of patients across 4 case studies: a simulation phase pilot performed in Finland and the three small scale pilot study run across Greece, Canada, Spain. It aims to study the transition from the hospital or rehabilitation setting to home settings through patients monitoring during their stay in the clinical settings and analysing the gathered data in order to create transparent and explicable support to doctors in order to enable them to take the right decisions for transition. The collected data, coming from ICT monitoring and intervention tools, are analysed and merged in order to provide higher level interpretable information to healthcare professionals and support their decision for the course of care. Also, monitoring capabilities have been provided in the user's home so that the healthcare professionals can gain insight on how the patient is progressing and adapt their care accordingly. Finally, in the context of the JRA2 an economic impact assessment has been conducted to evaluate the feasibility and advantages of gathering multichannel data across Living Labs, and to evaluate the economic implications of employing lower-cost home monitoring devices in contrast to pricier clinical setting monitoring tools.

Table 1. Overview of the Living Labs and organisations involved in JRA3

Abbreviation	Full (legal) name	Country
LAUREA	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	Finland
McGill	McGill University	Canada

Abbreviation	Full (legal) name	Country
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	Greece
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Spain

1.3 Purpose of the document

This deliverable includes the follow-up and results of the performed activities within JRA2 · Transitional Care pilots. It serves as an exploration of transitional care within healthcare, aiming to enhance our understanding and practices in this area that offers a panoramic view of transitional care practices, facilitating a deeper understanding of their broader implications. Derived from experiences in clinical and home settings, the document offers recommendations for healthcare professionals regarding transitional care timing, follow-up protocols, and readmission mitigation strategies. The deliverable summarizes key insights and implications drawn from the entire document, setting the stage for future advancements in transitional care practices. In carrying out these activities, this document contributes to enhancing transitional care practices aimed at helping healthcare providers, researchers and other stakeholders interested in improving patient’s transitions and increasing health system efficiency.

1.4 Document Structure

The document provides an in-depth navigation of the JRA2 on Transitional Care, with the aim of improving our understanding and practices in this area of healthcare. The structure is as such:

- **Section 1**, a comprehensive introduction and objectives of the JRA2 in various sections and outlines the structured of the deliverable.
- **Section 2** details small-scale pilot conducted in various geographic locations, such as Canada, Greece, Spain and a simulation pilot conducted in Finland. These pilots are outlined and cover targeted objectives, iterative phases and methodological aspects. In addition, this section details the implementation phase, showing the progress made and the services employed to facilitate transitional care with digital-based tools. Methodological assessments offer critical insight, while analysis of KPIs provides a foundation for understanding the effectiveness of transitional care interventions implemented. This section also explores the challenges, obstacles, and lessons learned from each pilot project, enriching our understanding of the complexities inherent in transitional care practices.
- **Section 3** expands on this exploration by presenting a harmonized analysis of all Living Labs involved in the Transitional Care activities, highlighting the common services offered, comparative outcomes, and comprehensive economic impact assessment.
- **Section 4** offers practical recommendations derived from a synthesis of clinical and home settings, enabling healthcare professionals to make informed decisions about the timing of transitional care, follow-up protocols, and strategies to mitigate readmission risks.
- **Section 5** offers a thoughtful conclusion, summarizing the main ideas and implications drawn from the entire document, thus laying the groundwork for future advances and improvements in transitional care practices.

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2 Case Studies Overview

Understanding and addressing the transitional needs of patients shifting between different care settings within the health sphere is highly imperative. As a part of JRA2 on Transitional Care, some case studies have been carried out to explore this complex scene. Among these are simulation pilots done in Finland, followed by three small scale pilots conducted across Greece, Canada and Spain. Each of these activities sought to interrogate and illuminate the fine requirements as well as challenges regarding transitions of patients thereby providing invaluable insights on improving the practice of transition care. These case studies aim to thoroughly examine transition needs for patients by using different geographical and health contexts. By examining objectives, methodologies, outcomes for these initiatives we get to know more about varied aspects of transitional care that eventually lay the ground for improved strategic direction on how patients can be supported during their critical periods of healthcare journey changes.

Table 2. Overview of co-creation sessions and small-scale pilot studies

	Finland · LAUREA <i>Simulation-based research</i>	Canada · McGill – CRIR <i>Small-scale pilot</i>	Greece · AUTH <i>Small-scale pilot</i>	Spain · UPM <i>Small-scale pilot</i>
Co-creation				
CP/Exp	Nursing students (n=40)	N/A	Healthcare professionals (n=30)	Healthcare professionals (n=9)
Pts/C	N/A	Patients with stroke (n=5)	N/A	NA
Small-scale pilot studies				
Aim	To evaluate the use of technology in enhancing nursing students' learning and students' learning experiences regarding transitional care simulations.	To evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors in traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors.	investigate the feasibility of collecting digital biomarkers in a hospital environment.	VITALES aimed to gather crucial data supporting transitional care, focusing on the period encompassing hospital discharge and home recovery by monitoring

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	Finland · LAUREA <i>Simulation-based research</i>	Canada · McGill – CRIR <i>Small-scale pilot</i>	Greece · AUTH <i>Small-scale pilot</i>	Spain · UPM <i>Small-scale pilot</i>
				patients recuperating at home following hip or knee replacement surgeries.
Status	Completed	Recruited 6 community-dwelling stroke survivors. Aiming to continue recruiting n=16 patients with stroke and traumatic brain injury.	Contacted: n= 11 Recruited: n= 7 Complete the study: n=5	Contacted: n= 51 Recruited: n= 18 Complete the study: n=10
IV	The study was based on two simulation scenarios in transitional care (postoperative ward and emergency department) involving nursing students (n=40).	To evaluate different wearable sensors for their suitability in integration into an online platform. We tested the Heel2Toe sensor during a one time in-person meeting with participants, during which we collected data during 2-minute tests of walking at both a normal pace and a fast pace. Additionally, participants were provided with the Fitbit smartwatch to wear for a period of two weeks.	Testing of the protocol for data collection in the “Hippokrateion” General Hospital of Thessaloniki	Install IoT devices in patients' homes, baseline assessments, and training, followed by a period where patients monitor themselves daily using the devices, with immediate support available for any encountered issues through various communication channels.

Note. CP = Care professionals with area of expertise, Exp = (Technical) experts, Pts = Patients, C = Citizens, MCI = Mind cognitive impairment, IV = Intervention details. NA = Not applicable.

2.1 Case Study 1. Simulation-based research (Laurea Simulated Hospital - Finland)

2.1.1 Small scale pilot study description

Objective and Phases

The simulation-based research's objective was to evaluate the use of technology in enhancing nursing students' learning and students' learning experiences regarding transitional care simulations. Following research questions were addressed:

1. Use of technology in simulation scenario
 - How do students perceive the use of camera techniques to support their learning in simulation?
2. Learning experiences related to the simulation scenario
 - What kind of learning experiences do students have about simulation scenarios?
 - How do students evaluate the simulation scenario?
 - Which pedagogical features do students perceive as meaningful in enhancing their learning?

The study consisted of simulation scenarios involving nursing students and feedback session after simulation scenarios.

2.1.2 Execution

The study was based on two simulation scenarios in transitional care (postoperative ward and emergency department) involving nursing students. The scenarios used standardized patients i.e., student-actors who were trained for their role. The cases were designed in detail based on the evidence-based information (e.g. concerning patient involvement, patient-centred care, individualized care). In addition to normal simulation control and recording system, point-of-view camera angles (GoPro Max- and Logitech Meet up-cameras) were used to record the activities from a patient's perspectives. The students had opportunity to examine and reflect the recorded activities after the simulation. Researchers/simulation instructor and the expert by experience observed the simulation, and they all participated in debriefing discussion after the simulation. The simulation scenarios were pilot tested among a group of students' prior simulation-based research

Convenience sampling was used to recruit nursing students in Laurea University of Applied Sciences for the simulation-based research. The students starting from the third study semester were eligible to participate. The simulation scenarios were integrated in the study units, and researchers and lecturers in charge of the study unit informed the students and asked voluntary students to participate. Voluntary students gave informed consent to participate. Altogether, 40 students in two Laurea campuses participated in the study. Out of them, 22 were fourth semester students and 18 third semester students.

2.1.2.1 Living Lab services

Expert opinions and advisory services from the Living Lab were utilized to design the simulation scenarios. An expert-by-experience participated in the planning and execution of the simulation-based research to enhance the service user perspective in the simulation scenarios. The involvement of the expert by experience was found to be very relevant because, based on his own experience, he was able to provide examples of challenges or problems related to the transitional care. This increased the authenticity of the scenarios, and experts by experience can be recommended to be used more extensively when investigating healthcare processes.

The small-scale pilot was strongly based on the *simulation test* service, as the research was conducted in a simulated environment. The simulation environment provides an opportunity to create a variety of real-world clinical situations where treatment processes can be studied and investigated.

Usability testing was integrated in the simulations to test whether the use of point-of-view cameras can enhance nursing students' learning on patient involvement in transitional care.

Research site permit was applied from Laurea University of Applied Sciences as it is always needed when conducting research among Laurea's students.

2.1.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Evaluation and KPIs

Data were collected after the simulation scenarios in Laurea's campuses in October and November 2022. The data were collected using group discussions and a structured questionnaire.

The group discussions focused on students' perceptions about the use of point-of-view camera angle and their learning experiences and feedback about simulation. The structured feedback questionnaire focused on simulations' support in learning, the use of point-of-view camera angle and feasibility of the simulation scenarios and arrangements. In the group discussions, the students wrote down their perceptions on post-it notes, discussed them, and compiled them into A3 sheets. The questionnaire was provided in electronic form for the students, who answered it after the simulation scenarios and debriefing.

Analysis

Group discussion data were analysed using qualitative content analysis. The descriptive statistics were used to analyse the structured data.

Students' perceptions about the use of point-of-view camera recording

Regarding the use of point-of-view camera recording in the simulation, *nursing students perceived it supporting their learning, brought out some critical viewpoints and made suggestions for the future use*. Overall, the students perceived that use of point-of-view camera recording enables them to see the situation from the patient's perspective, thus, "putting oneself in the patient's place". This enables for example investigating professionals' gestures, expressions, and movement, and makes the simulation more authentic. Furthermore, it improves the understanding of how one would like to be encountered by healthcare professionals. Students perceived that watching the point-of-view recording after the simulation session allowed them to evaluate their own performance more objectively and made their strengths and development needs more visible, and based on that, they can modify their actions in the future. Watching the recording helped them to recall the simulation session and reflect their performance afterwards. Some students also perceived that point-of-view camera recording created positive pressure in the simulation, which supported their learning. However, *critical viewpoints* were brought out as some students felt that the presence of the camera made them feel nervous.

Nursing *students suggested* that point-of-view camera recording would be used more often, even in all simulations and in advanced life support training. They also suggested using multiple camera angles e.g., recording the simulation scenario both from a patient's and a nurse's perspectives. The students brought out the possibility of using point-of-view camera recording also in clinical practice e.g., in producing guidance material for the patients.

Students' feedback about the simulation scenario

Altogether, 39 out of 40 nursing students (97,5%) gave feedback by answering the electronic questionnaire (Table 3). Students' feedback was very positive in general as most of them felt that the simulation scenarios supported their learning in transitional care and patient involvement. Most students felt that participation of the expert by experience in simulation deepened their understanding of the patient perspective. The majority of the students evaluated that the use of point-of-view camera recording supported their learning in patient involvement, and it could be used in the future simulations. The students preferred GoPro-camera as a method of recording.

Table 3. Students' feedback

	Simulation scenario supported my learning in transitional care (n=39)		Simulation scenario supported my learning in patient involvement (n=39)		Participation of the expert by experience in simulation deepened my understanding of the patient perspective (n=39)		The use of point-of-view camera recording supported my learning in patient involvement (n=39)		The use of point-of-view camera recording could be used in the future simulations as well (n=39)		Which camera technique was more useful in learning? (n=39)		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Meet up	GoPro	Can't say
Strongly agree	15	39	17	44	21	54	16	41	25	64			
Agree	17	44	19	49	10	26	16	41	7	18	n=10	n=19	n=10
Neither agree nor disagree	2	5	2	5	5	13	1	2	1	2	26%	48%	26%
Disagree	1	2	0	0	2	5	3	8	3	8			
Strongly disagree	4	10	1	2	1	2	3	8	3	8			

Discussion

Overall, students perceived that the use of simulation scenarios and camera angles supported their learning in transitional care. The involvement of an expert by experience was also perceived to support learning. Patient-centred approach and support for patient involvement are key elements in successful transitional care. According to students, the pedagogical and technical solutions used in the simulations supported the learning of these essential elements. By strengthening the patient's perspective in simulation teaching by recording the activities from patient's perspective and making use of expert by experience in scenario planning and debriefing discussions, the capabilities of future nurses could be developed to promote patient involvement in transitional care. However, it should be noted that this was a small pilot study and future learning experiences would need to be studied in a broader sample.

2.1.4 Conclusions

Based on this pilot study, it can be recommended to use point-of-view camera angles more extensively in simulation exercises. Their use could also be examined in other contexts when looking at healthcare processes from the patient's perspective. Experts by experience should be used more in nurse education to strengthen the patient's perspective.

2.2 Case Study 2. Feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors to capture mobility in traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors: Descriptive mixed-methods study (McGill - CRIR Living Lab Canada)

2.2.1 Small scale pilot study description

This descriptive study used a simultaneous mixed method design to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors in traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors. Simultaneous mixed methods design consists of collecting both quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously, analyzing the data separately and then merging them at the point of interpretation or discussion to determine whether there is convergence, difference or another possible combination between the two types of data (Fortin & Gagnon, 2016). Collecting both quantitative and qualitative data allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the feasibility of using wearable sensors in monitoring and improving outcomes for traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors.

Context

This study is an extension of a previous larger study aiming to develop a Web-based platform: Electronic Mobility Monitoring and Intervention system (EMMI). The results of the VITALISE study will be used to further improve the development of the EMMI platform. The goal of the EMMI platform is to optimize mobility and individuals' participation in work and social roles by providing: 1) continuous remote monitoring of mobility outcomes; 2) delivering individualized evidence-based interventions for individuals with ABI; 3) integrating the information into rehabilitation health services and community care.

Mobility refers to a person's ability to move independently and safely from one point to another, which is necessary to accomplish activities of daily living and for participation in different life and societal roles (Alhasani et al., 2022). Utilizing wearable sensors is one of the strategies planned to provide continuous remote monitoring of mobility outcomes. By identifying feasible and acceptable wearable sensors through the current study, we aim to inform the customization and refinement of desired features to capture patient data within the EMMI platform.

Ethics

We are amending ethics for VITALISE project to examine the feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors to capture mobility in traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors.

Participants

Participants who were recruited in the larger study EMMI project were selected by convenience to participate in the current study within the VITALISE project, based on the following criteria: Expressed an interest in testing wearable sensors during phase 2 of the project, do not present any major incapacity limiting their use of the wearables (ex, Fracture, severe cognitive impairment). We targeted participants with diverse sociodemographic profiles to better understand the factors that may impact the use behavior of the sensors. We excluded participants with Severe cognitive impairment (e.g. inability to communicate and understand) or terminal or severe illness with a survival prognosis of less than 18 months.

2.2.2 Execution

2.2.2.1 Testing Protocol

We aimed to assess various wearable sensors to determine their suitability for integration into the EMMI platform. However, due to resource constraints, we conducted the testing sequentially using available sensors acquired by our research team and participants who completed phase 2 of the EMMI study. The current study focused on presenting the results of testing Fitbits and Heel2toe devices to evaluate their feasibility and acceptability among community dwelling individuals living with stroke or traumatic brain injury.

Heel2Toe is a wearable sensor that attaches to the side of the shoe to collect data related on walking quality such as foot pressure, stride length, and cadence(Alhasani et al., 2022). The collected data is then transmitted to an online app, allowing users to track their walking, or running performance and identify any abnormalities or potential issues (PhysioBiometrics, s. f.). With the help of Heel2toe wearable sensors, individuals could get valuable insights into their walking quality, making it easier to improve performance, prevent injuries, and optimize overall their mobility and social participation.

Fitbit, a popular fitness tracker brand, has also introduced wearable sensors in their products that monitor various aspects of physical activity(*Site officiel de Fitbit*, s. f.). These sensors can be worn on the wrist (smartwatch), providing users with a comprehensive overview of their daily activities. Fitbit activity trackers capture information like number of steps, distance walked throughout the day, duration and quality of sleep and heart rate(*Site officiel de Fitbit*, s. f.). By integrating this data with the Heel2Toe sensors' information, this could help provide comprehensive monitoring of mobility and functional outcomes in traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors living in the community, ultimately leading to more personalized and effective rehabilitation plans.

Electronic patient-reported outcomes (E-PRO) is another strategy to be used to provide continuous monitoring of health-related information obtained directly from the patient. A patient's description of their symptoms, their level of satisfaction with their care, and how an illness or therapy impacts their physical, mental, emotional, spiritual, and social well-being are a few examples of patient-reported outcomes (NCI Dictionary of Cancer Terms - NCI, s. f.). In the current study we used two patient reported outcomes: the Patient Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System 29 V2.0 (Hays et al., 2018) and EQ-5D-5L (Devlin et al., 2020). The PROMIS-29 v2.0 profile evaluates pain intensity and seven health domains namely physical function, fatigue, pain interference, depressive symptoms, anxiety, ability to participate in social roles and activities, and sleep disturbance (Hays et al., 2018). The EQ-5D-5L evaluates 6 health domains including mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain or discomfort and anxiety or depression (Devlin et al., 2020).

2.2.2.2 Testing procedure

First Visit

- Participants underwent a series of patient reported outcomes (PROMIS29 and EQ-5D-5L)
- The facilitator explained how Heel2toe functions and how it should be worn.
- Testing of Heel2toe was conducted to gather data on walking quality. Participants were asked to wear the sensor for at least 4 minutes. During this period, they were encouraged to walk around the room at a fast pace for 2 minutes and at a normal pace for another 2 minutes. Data were collected for both the affected and less affected feet.
- The facilitator provided in-person instructions on the proper method of wearing Fitbit and charging the sensor.
- An information sheet detailing the Fitbit usage guidelines was supplied to participants.
- Feedback preferences regarding the Heel2Toe and E-PRO were collected.

At home (14 Days)

- Participants were instructed to wear the FitBit sensor continuously for 24 hours a day, engaging in their usual activities, and recharge them overnight.
- Each participant received a guideline for daily usage and maintenance of the sensor.

Second Visit (After 14 Days)

- Participants returned the Fitbit sensor during the second visit.
- They participated in a semi-structured interview to capture their experience with Fitbit, feedback preferences, and report any adverse events or technical problems that might have influenced their behavior.
- They participated in a survey to assess the usability of the device.

1-month follow-up call

- The facilitator contacted the participants by phone and collected again the patient reported outcomes from the 1st visit (PROMIS29 and EQ-5D-5L).

2.2.2.3 Living Lab services

We conducted a feasibility study aimed at testing wearables among traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors, with the goal of evaluating the feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors within these populations. This small-scale descriptive study reported testing results with wearables during transitional care, specifically focusing on the feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors among traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors.

2.2.3 Outcomes and Analysis

2.2.3.1 Evaluation methodology

Quantitative Data

Mobility outcomes. The PROMIS-29 and EQ-5D-5L instruments were utilized to assess health-related quality of life, encompassing physical, social, and emotional well-being, and health status along with functional activities, respectively (Devlin et al., 2020; Hays et al., 2018). To score the PROMIS-29, the raw score for each of its 7 health dimensions was transformed into a T-score with

a standard error (SE) using the scoring table provided by PROMIS (PROMIS, 2021). As for scoring the EQ-5D-5L, its 5 health dimensions are each subdivided into 5 levels of perceived problems: Level 1 indicates no problem, Level 2 indicates slight problems, Level 3 indicates moderate problems, Level 4 indicates severe problems, and Level 5 indicates extreme problems. The PROMIS-29 has demonstrated good reliability and construct validity in patients with chronic pain. The EQ-5D-3L has also demonstrated a good construct validity in both stroke and traumatic brain injury survivors (Geraerds et al., 2020; Mahesh et al., 2019) and good reliability in stroke survivors (Mahesh et al., 2019).

Usability. The System Usability Scale is a ten-item scale giving an overview of subjective assessments of system usability (Brooke, 1986). The scale was specifically used to capture the usability of FitBit during the period of 14 days. The scale was shown to be reliable and valid (Peres et al., 2013).

Feasibility data. We collected the number of participants recruited; time to complete assessments; percentage of missing data; effort in developing the training; any adverse events or technical problems; time required to familiarize with the wearable sensors; During follow-ups: readmission (including the time during which the event occurred, and treatment followed) and occurrence of any health complications.

Qualitative Data

During the second visit, participants were invited to complete a semi structured interview to better understand the factors that may influence use behavior of the FitBit and their use experience. The interview guideline was developed based on a previous study that explored the feedback preferences when using sensors in stroke survivors (Demers et al., 2023).

The distribution of the qualitative and quantitative data collection across time is reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Description of the timeline of data collection

Timeline	1 st visit	14 days among visits	2 nd visit	1 month follow up
Data collection	EQ-5D-5L	Fitbit data (steps, distance, heart rate, sleep duration and quality)	Adapted System Usability Scale	EQ-5D-3L
	PROMIS-29		Semi-structured interview	PROMIS-29
	Preferences on Feedback			
	Quality of walking: Heel2toe			Readmission or adverse events
	Sociodemographic information			
	Feasibility data			

Analysis

Association between data captured through the wearables and mobility outcomes were analyzed to identify the correlation between digital biomarkers with patient reported outcomes. Pearson

correlation for normally distributed data and Spearman correlation in cases of non-normal distribution were applied. Descriptive statistics for sociodemographic, clinical characteristics of participants, usability and feasibility data were also conducted.

Interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns in participants' experiences and perceptions of wearing the sensors. This qualitative data will provide valuable insights into the acceptability and usability of the wearables in real-world settings, complementing the quantitative findings from the statistical analysis.

2.2.3.2 Quantitative results

Feasibility data

We recruited six community dwelling stroke survivors with different sociodemographic profiles (See Table 5); they have completed the first visit assessments; the second visit assessment was undergoing as of the time this report was written. Due to unanticipated delays in EMMI project protocol modification and ethics review, we have encountered delays in participant recruitment for the current study.

Table 5. Sociodemographic profiles

	Age groups			
	35-44		55+	
	Female	Male	Female	Male
EMMI03				x
EMMI05				x
EMMI06				x
EMMI08				x
EMMI09				x
EMMI11	x			

The test conducted with Heel2Toe was onsite during the first visit; the participants were not trained to use it; however, they received various feedback from using it and were asked to give their preferences regarding the type of feedback they wanted to receive. Figure 1 shows screenshots of several types of feedback that Heel2toe platform provides. Participants expressed their interest in receiving specific feedback related to gait quality metrics (e.g., Heel strike, Toe push off, power phase, balance phase, foot clearance) (See Figure 2).

D6.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA2

Figure 1. Physiobiometric platform: feedback after the Heel2Toe testing

D6.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA2

Figure 2. Physiobiometric platform: feedback preferred by study participants

During the testing, a lot of difficulties were encountered: the sensor stopped working suddenly, the app was not recording accurately the time during which the sensor was being tested, and there were delays in accessing the feedback on the platform.

The FitBit training session, lasting 30 minutes, included an overview of the app, synchronization instructions, a demonstration of FitBit features, and an explanation of its attributes. Participants displayed confidence in navigating the app and synchronizing their devices, although initial attempts sometimes faced challenges. Nevertheless, their persistence and motivation ensured success. Our feasibility data collection plan for the second visit includes monitoring readmissions and health complications. Two participants contacted the research team because they were unsure if they should have brought the heel2toe sensor along with their Fitbit or if they should have brought it at all. One participant admitted forgetting to synchronize their device since the initial visit, prompting a reminder from our research assistant. No participant contacted us about any technical issues with the Fitbit.

Mobility outcomes

Promis-29 and EQ5 results collected during Visit1 are reported in Table 6 and Table 7. The participants are at the date of this report undergoing the 2 weeks test with Fitbit.

Table 6. Description of the PROMIS-29 participants' scores according to health dimension and age groups

	Age groups					
	35-44		55+			
<i>Promis-29 Health dimension</i>	ID11; T-score(SE)	ID03; T-score(SE)	ID05; T-score(SE)	ID06; T-score(SE)	ID08; T-score(SE)	ID09; T-score(SE)
<i>Physical Function</i>	35,6 (2,3)	41,9 (2,5)	37,9 (2,3)	36,7 (2,3)	57 (6,6)	45,5 (2,8)
<i>Anxiety</i>	55,8 (2,7)	59,5 (2,6)	59,5 (2,6)	61,4 (2,6)	51,2 (3,1)	55,8 (2,7)

	Age groups					
<i>Depression</i>	55,7 (2,3)	53,9 (2,4)	62,2 (2,3)	58,9 (2,3)	41 (6,2)	41 (6,2)
<i>Fatigue</i>	57 (2,3)	55,1 (2,4)	57 (2,3)	48,6 (2,5)	48,6 (2,5)	43,1 (2,7)
<i>Sleep disturbance</i>	43,8 (3,5)	52,4 (3,4)	63,8 (3,4)	52,4 (3,4)	48,4 (3,4)	48,4 (3,4)
<i>Ability to participate in social roles</i>	42,3 (2,3)	48,1 (2,2)	48,1 (2,2)	44,2 (2,3)	64,2 (5,1)	51,9 (2,2)
<i>Pain interference</i>	61,2 (1,8)	49,6 (2,5)	63,8 (1,8)	62,5 (1,8)	53,9 (1,9)	49,6 (2,5)

Table 7. Frequency of reported problems for study participants by health dimension and age group

Instrument	Health dimension		Age groups		Total
			35-44	55+	
EQ-3D-5L	Mobility	No problems		2	2
		Problems	1	3	4
	Self-care	No problems	1	2	3
		Problems		3	3
	Usual Activity	No problems		2	2
		Problems	1	3	4
	Pain / Discomfort	No problems		1	1
		Problems	1	4	5
	Anxiety / Depression	No problems	1	1	2
		Problems		4	4

2.2.3.3 Qualitative results

Four main themes emerged from the qualitative data analysis: (1) Interest in visualizing performance and health progress, (2) Concerns about wearing sensors, (3) Value of continuous follow-up after discharge. and (4) Perceived value in using wearable sensors. Each emergent theme is summarized and accompanied by exemplary quotes from individual participants, denoted by their respective identifiers (e.g., EMMI#).

Theme 1: Interest in visualizing performance and health progress: This theme encompassed the participants interests in visualizing their progress when using wearable technology to encourage better performance and healthier behavior. Visual feedback was described as graphs accompanied with statistics comparing data collected on different timeline to capture any change on the performance or health status. Participants reported that the feedback metrics extracted from

Heel2Toe platform were clear and easy to understand; however, they expressed a clear preference for gait quality feedback (as described in previous section).

EMMI06: “More visual you know, at least you don't have, I don't know, any curve, I have the impression that at least that you say well I've regressed but I can go back up”

EMMI09: “Well personally I'd see it more visually.”

Theme 2: Concerns about wearing sensors

Several participants expressed discomfort with the appearance of the Heel2Toe and the way it sits on the shoe, with the sensor often likened to the device worn by ‘prisoners’. The same participants said they did not feel comfortable wearing it in public. On the other hand, only one participant expressed a preference for wearing it on the ankle rather than in the shoe, as it was more comfortable. Forgetting to wear the sensor was also reported by several participants, who tended to forget tasks to do following their stroke. Continuous data collection through sensors, or when applications associated with these sensors send several notifications a day, were also seen by participants as potentially intrusive. Only one participant reported difficulty reading the FitBit's screen because it was too small.

EMMI06: “my strap is really tight, I think I'd rather have it on my ankle.”

EMMI05: “For me it's something I'll always forget (to wear).”

Theme 3: Value of continuous follow-up after discharge

Participants reported inadequate follow-up after their discharge, citing a lack of resources and difficulty accessing key individuals for feedback on their condition. In parallel, they perceived advantages of using electronic patient reported outcomes or wearable sensors to continuously collect data on their health status; emphasizing the importance of accessing resources and interventions promptly when feedback indicates deterioration or a need for change. They indicated that the frequency of the follow-up should not be less than 2 weeks to be able to detect change; with a three-month period deemed appropriate by most participants.

EMMI05: “The only person who asked me about my condition was my family doctor, and I haven't had a family doctor since the end of February. ... who's going to ask me that question in a month, 2 months?... There aren't enough people doing follow-up”

EMMI08: “You can see, you can remember. Like what? How it was before and how it is now. You know... So yeah, like every three months.”

Theme 4: Perceived Value in using wearable sensors

According to the participants, feedback from wearable sensors could offer innate insights that enable individuals to act on the information received. They saw wearable sensors as tools for encouraging the adoption of healthy habits in their daily lives. Additionally, it was emphasized that participants might enhance their ability for problem-solving and learn appropriate ways to respond to minimize negative consequences or preserve development.

EMMI08: “If I'm not doing enough of the activity that has to notify me maybe to do some more, you know... And then if we identify the problem, then we can approach this problem and we can deal with this problem.”

EMMI03: “if It was a minimum threshold of steps to take in a day, so if I take 10,000 steps in a day, I lose nothing.”

2.2.3.4 Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of wearable sensors in traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors. Preliminary analysis of quantitative and qualitative data highlighted personal and contextual factors that may influence participants' use and acceptability of wearable sensors. Among personal factors, concerns about wearing the sensors such as discomfort with the appearance and size of the FitBit screen, as well as difficulty accessing key people for feedback;

preferences for visual feedback. The value of continuous follow-up after discharge was emphasized, with participants stating that it is essential to access resources and interventions promptly when feedback indicates deterioration or a need for change. The participants saw wearable sensors as tools for encouraging healthy habits and problem-solving, enhancing their ability to minimize negative consequences or preserve development. They also emphasized the importance of setting a minimum threshold of steps to take in a day to avoid losing anything. Contextual factors included mainly accessibility to resources that can support sensor use in the event of technical difficulties and problems. These results highlight the importance of developing appropriate strategies to overcome potential obstacles and maximize the benefits of wearable sensor use.

The results of our study partly echo those of other studies, which highlight the importance placed by stroke survivors on visual feedback for self-monitoring (Demers et al., 2023). In addition, previous studies have shown that combining visual feedback with auditory or haptic feedback could help maximize benefits (Wang et al., 2017). Prompt action on feedback is crucial to ensure that individuals can make the necessary adjustments to their behavior and improve results. In addition, incorporating personalized feedback tailored to individual needs and preferences can further enhance the effectiveness of using wearable sensors in self-monitoring (van Ommeren et al., 2018). Offering feedback as part of goal-setting is another effective strategy for motivating individuals to adopt healthier behaviors (Lehrer et al., 2021). By setting achievable goals and providing feedback on progress, individuals are more likely to remain motivated and committed to implementing positive lifestyle changes (Lehrer et al., 2021).

2.2.4 Conclusions

In conclusion, our study highlights the promising role of wearable sensors in monitoring health outcomes among traumatic brain injury and stroke survivors. Participants emphasized the importance of continuous follow-up, personalized feedback and timely interventions or action plan. Moving forward, addressing concerns and enhancing resource accessibility will be essential for maximizing the benefits of wearable sensor use in this population.

2.3 Case Study 3. Digital Biomarkers for Supporting Transitions in care (ThessAHALL-AUTH, Greece)

2.3.1 Small scale pilot study description

The study of Digital Biomarkers for Supporting Transitions in care, was run by the Thessaloniki Active and Healthy Ageing Living Lab (ThessAHALL), as part of the Horizon 2020 VITALISE project, aimed to investigate crucial information required to enhance transitional care and standardize procedures across Living Labs. It particularly focused on transitional care and integrating data gathered through technological instruments, patient-reported outcome measures, and clinical evaluations to identify challenges and constraints in the activity and mobility of individuals with disabilities or complex chronic conditions.

The research objective was to investigate the feasibility of collecting digital biomarkers in a hospital environment. Our goal was to identify the difficulties that healthcare professionals face with the use of ICT devices, the additional burden they have, the possible data loss from the collection of data in real life environments and the patient characteristics that can influence data collection.

D6.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA2

Figure 3. Transitional Care Pilot at Thess-AHALL Living Lab

The study was performed in three phases as described in the initial protocol (see D6.1 Submission of research protocol in peer reviewed journal for JRA2). In the co-creation phase, health professionals and formal caregivers have engaged in co-creation activities. The objective of these sessions was:

- the current clinical practice used for informing transitions and the issues/challenges that arise from them
- identify the tendencies and willingness of healthcare professionals to use technological tools for collecting information to support their decisions on transitional process

AUTH performed in total 3 co-creation sessions with 30 participants. The data were collected anonymously by session observers that were taking detailed notes. In the testing and simulation phase, the research team deployed and tested all the technologies in the Health Care Transitions Living Lab “Asterios Karagiannis” in the “Hippokraton” General Hospital of Thessaloniki. The testing revealed several challenges that resulted in an ethics amendment and modifications of the protocol that are reported in the next Section.

The running phase included the pilot testing of the fully operational system, installing all the sensors presented in Table 8 inside a hospital room and in the Healthcare Transitions Living Lab of “Hippokraton” General Hospital of Thessaloniki. Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking devices are continuously and unobtrusively collecting data, while the rest of the devices are used by the attending clinician daily.

Table 8. Presentation of the devices used and collected data

Device category	Device model	Data collected	Collection point
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	Mentorage Depth Cameras	Number of Posture Transitions per Hour	Hospital ward and Living Lab
		Percentage of Posture per Hour	
	Fitbit Charge 5	Daily Steps	Hospital ward and Living Lab
		Sleep duration	
		Walking distance	
	Heel2Toe	Percentage of bad steps	Living Lab
		Percentage of good steps	
	Withings Body+	Weight	Hospital ward

Device category	Device model	Data collected	Collection point
Body size and composition		Fat Mass	
		Lean Mass	
		Water Mass	
		Bone Mass	
		Muscle Mass	
		BMI	
		Datetime	
(Primary) Vital signs	Omron M700 Intelli IT	Systolic	Hospital ward
		Diastolic	
		Pulse	
		Datetime	
	Beurer FT 95	Body temperature	Hospital ward
		Datetime	
	Berrymed Oxymeter	Blood oxygen saturation	Hospital ward
		Datetime	

The participants were initially screened by the three attending clinicians based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients over 65 years of age
- Reason for admission to hospital: diagnosis of multimorbidity including stroke/cerebral injury, stroke/osteoarthritis, post-operative patient, or cardiovascular disease
- Patient hospitalized or recently (within one week) discharged from hospital or rehabilitation center
- Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS) score <7

Exclusion Criteria:

- Severe cognitive impairment (e.g., inability to communicate and understand)
- Severe physical disability (e.g., quadriplegia)
- Terminal or severe illness with a survival prognosis of less than 18 months
- Persons living in a supported living facility
- People who are unable to give informed consent

Data collection occurred using technological tools, patient-reported outcome measures, and clinical assessments to gather information on activity, mobility, and functionality during hospitalization. Data collection took place at 3 different stages within the hospital environment:

- 1) During hospitalization
- 2) During discharge at the Living Lab at the “Hippokrateion” General Hospital of Thessaloniki

3) Within 1 week after discharge

More specifically, during hospitalization patients underwent various psychological questionnaires and assessments, such as EuroQol (EQ-5D-5L), Health status, SF-12/Health-related quality of life (physical, social, emotional health), Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) for Depression, Lawton IADL for Functionality etc.

During Discharge, patients stayed for approximately half an hour in the Living Lab and were asked to follow a morning routine aimed at gathering data that reflects real-life scenarios in a discreet and non-intrusive manner. This routine included a series of activities designed to assess daily functioning and behavior, such as getting out of bed, preparing and eating breakfast, watching TV, reading aloud from a newspaper or book to capture linguistic features, and making a phone call to a relative or nurse. Additionally, a doctor was present to supervise the process and ensure the safety and well-being of the patients.

The collected data were pseudonymized with personal codes for each participant and made accessible to the project's scientific collaborators. Data sets were minimized to share only the minimum required to avoid potential risks.

2.3.2 Execution

2.3.2.1 Living Lab services

- **Co-creation sessions:** conducted workshops to gather information supporting the transitional care process, focusing on evaluating the feasibility, efficacy, and benefit of collecting multi-channel data utilizing IoT devices, and investigating the collection and use of digital biomarkers and PROMs
- **Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study:** we gathered feedback from clinicians throughout the study in order to understand the challenges that they were facing during the data collection. The feedback gathered will help improve the study and the feasibility of the concept in real clinical settings.
- **Expert opinion and advisory services:** we utilized this service to gather input about the ethics submission and also the real life implementation of the concept by clinicians. This service was offered as a consultation by the broader Living Lab team, not included in the core research study team.
- **Legal, regulatory, and safety standard support:** ensured informed consent from participants, and implemented measures to protect data privacy and security.
- **Small-scale real life testing and experimentation:** executed the pilot to test the solution in a real-life setting, closely monitoring patients
- **Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping:** Before the study protocol preparation, a stakeholder and partner analysis was performed in order to identify the hospital clinic within out network that will be appropriate for undertaking the patient recruitment.
- **(Data) Access management:** implemented procedures for data access like specific access point, security codes
- **Data analysis:** qualitative and quantitative analysis of the collected data
- **Data anonymization and pseudonymization:** data pseudonymization for sharing information with VITALISE colleagues
- **Data cleaning:** preprocessing of the data coming from the sensors
- **Data management plan:** description of data access, data sharing procedures
- **Detailed project planning:** preparation of a rollout agenda for pilot execution
- **Dissemination:** presentation of the outcomes at the VITALISE final event – Health & Wellbeing Living Lab summit
- **Ethical application preparation:** applied to the AUTH ethics committee, obtained approval, ensured informed consent from participants
- **Living lab project management:** management of resources, time and budget throughout the pilot execution phase

- **Research protocol design:** the protocol was published at the beginning of the study in JMIR research protocols
- **Results reporting / Publication writing:** preparation of a common publication about the co-creation results
- **Stakeholder engagement:** engagement of a total of 30 participants in the co-creation sessions (clinicians, healthcare professionals and family members), contacted a total of 11 patients that were admitted in the “Hippokration” General Hospital of Thessaloniki
- **Prototype testing:** Conducted testing in a control environment in the premises of the Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Laboratory prior piloting the solution in a real-life setting

2.3.2.2 Changes from the initial protocol

Some adjustments have been made to the protocol, based on the observations made during the testing phase. Initially, the threshold for the Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS) score was set at less than four. However, after careful consideration of patient demographics and clinical outcomes, it was considered appropriate to raise this threshold to less than seven. The CFS score was set initially to ensure that the patients have the appropriate mobility status in order to perform the requested measurements. The adjustment ensures a more inclusive approach while still maintaining the protocol's focus on frail patients. Additionally, the exclusion criterion of scoring less than 25 on the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) test has been removed to prevent potentially excluding patients who may still benefit from participation despite mild cognitive impairment. Another notable change involves replacing smart insoles with heel2Toe devices. This decision was driven by considerations of data accessibility, and cost-effectiveness as the smart insoles were purchased by a private company and there were difficulties in accessing the raw data. Furthermore, unexpected changes to the protocol, such as amendments in ethics submissions and device changes, posed challenges and time constraints during recruitment. Adjusting the initial patient enrolment projections reflects a practical evaluation of recruitment feasibility. By aligning with the available resources and addressing logistical constraints, these adaptations ensure a more robust and realistic recruitment strategy.

2.3.3 Outcomes and Analysis

Descriptive multi-method analysis

The clinicians of the “Hippokrateion” General hospital were screening all the admitted patients in the 2nd Pathology Clinic for identifying potential participants based on the expected hospitalization days, the reason for hospital admission and their mobility status. They identified and contacted 11 potential participants however, only 7 individuals agreed to take part, with 4 individuals opting out due to feeling uncomfortable in participating in the hospital setting. Nevertheless, only 5 individuals concluded the preliminary phase, with 2 drop-outs throughout the study primarily attributed to discomfort and worsening of health conditions during hospitalization.

Even though the sample size of 5 patients is not big enough for performing statistical analysis, a rich number of data was produced regarding the feasibility of the study. Our outcomes can also result in future recommendations for studies using ICT devices in clinical environments. The triangulation method was used to perform a descriptive analysis from multi-modal data. Triangulation can help increase validity of the results while also helping researchers to grasp the various perspectives of the phenomenon. Four different data sources were used in the triangulation analysis. Firstly, we identified from the literature search the reported challenges and group them into main themes. The co-creation data were analyzed and grouped into categories by two independent researchers using emergent coding techniques. A similar approach was used also with the attending clinicians provided information. Having as a starting point the literature findings, we mapped the co-creation outcomes and clinician reported information into the identified issues from literature. The results were complemented and supported by insights from the data gathered through the devices.

Outcomes

Table 9 and Table 10 below presents the descriptive statistics for demographics and clinical characteristics of participants.

Table 9. Patients demographics

Characteristic	Value
Age	70 ± 7.25 years
Gender (male/female)	3 females, 2 males

Table 10. Patients clinical characteristics

Scale	Scale description	Patient distribution
MoCA Score out of 30	Cognitive impairment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 25: None 18–25: Mild cognitive impairment 10–17: Moderate cognitive impairment < 10: Severe cognitive impairment 	Normal, n=1 patient Mild cognitive impairment, n=3 patients Moderate cognitive impairment, n=1 patient
PHQ-9 Score out of 27	Depression severity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0-4: none-minimal 5-9: mild 10-14: moderate 15-19: moderately severe 20-27: severe 	Mild, n=3 patients Moderate, n=2 patients
CFS Score 1-9	Frailty: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Very Fit Well Managing Well Vulnerable Mildly Frail Moderately Frail Severely Frail Very Severely Frail Terminally Ill 	2 Well, n=1 patient 4 Vulnerable, n=2 patients 6 moderately frail, n=2 patients
SF-12 Score for PCS out of 100 Score for MCS out of 100	Physical Component Summary (PCS): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >50 better than average physical health <50 poorer-than-average physical health Mental Component Summary (MCS): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >50 better-than-average mental health <50 poorer-than-average mental health 	PCS Poorer than average, n=5 patients MCS better-than-average, n=2 patients Poorer than average, n=3 patients

Three main themes emerged from the qualitative data analysis of the literature, co-creation and pilot testing data:

1. external factors that concern the system and the devices being used and are outside of the control of the patients or clinicians
2. factors related to the clinician's experience and perception that can directly influence their attitude towards the system and
3. factors related to the patient's experience and perception that can indirectly influence the clinician.

Table 11. Summary of the results

Main themes	Literature	Co-creation	Clinician implementation notes
External factors	Connectivity issues (Mansoor Baig et al., n.d.)		Clinician must repeat measurements to avoid data loss
	Power supply (Iqbal et al., 2016)		Devices battery level check and continuous power supply
	Adequate infrastructures (Davis et al., 2014)	Lack of infrastructure	Extra room for monitoring
Clinician experience and perception	Clinical benefits for patients (Lanham et al., n.d.)	Clinicians not perceiving the value	Perceived lack of benefit and poor understanding of research objectives
	Physician's ease of use (Hogaboam & Daim, 2018)	Time and resources to use the information	
	Productivity impact (Hogaboam & Daim, 2018)	Negative Perceived Productivity impact	
	Ease of data access (Hogaboam & Daim, 2018)	All the information should be accessible by all the stakeholders in real time	
Patient experience and perception	User acceptance and engagement (Mansoor Baig et al., n.d.)		Difficulty in adhering to monitoring protocol
	Perceived control and interactivity (Park et al., 2016)		Challenges in engaging the patient

Each emergent theme is summarized and accompanied by further explanation, utilizing also the quantitative data from the devices:

External factors

Device and system/technology connectivity is one of the main external factors that is reported in the literature as a cause of challenges in data collection, frequently resulting in data loss. It can also cause frustration to the clinicians if data synchronization is not working properly. This is an issue that

was not identified during the co-creation sessions but became obvious during the pilot testing. The attending clinician reported that the sensitivity of monitoring devices, such as the smart scales, posed challenges in accurate data collection, leading to inconsistencies in measurements and hindering patient monitoring. The clinicians had to repeat the measurement to avoid data loss which caused irritation to the patient.

In one specific case, a patient with moderately frail mobility (CFS score of 6) encountered challenges during both weighing and Heel2Toe measurements. Due to the requirement of the scale to remain still for at least 3 seconds with the entire foot on it for precise readings, gathering additional data beyond weight was not feasible. The patient faced further complications during measurements due to the progression of their condition. Consequently, conducting Heel2Toe measurements proved impossible, highlighting how frailty can hinder certain data collection procedures. Insights from the data collected via the Fitbit device provided further context, with a recorded average of 60.25 steps per day for this patient indicated a limitation in both mobility and overall activity levels.

On the other hand, another patient with a similar CFS score of 6 and an average of 45 steps per day managed to complete the same measurements without significant interruption. This successful completion our decision to adjust the criteria to include patients with a CFS score under 7 (CFS<7). By including patients within this range, we ensure that individuals who can effectively participate in the required measurements are not excluded.

It is also worth mentioning that clinicians cannot identify whether or when patients removed their Fitbit devices, as there was no alert or indication provided by the device itself. Consequently, we solely relied on the patients' self-reports regarding consistent wear. This fact introduces a challenge in accurately determining whether low step counts result from low physical activity or occasions where patients may have temporarily removed the Fitbit, leading to an underestimation of the actual activity levels. It's essential also to mention the absence of night sleep data on the first day that was caused by logistical factors such as the timing of Fitbit device distribution in the study. For instance, if a patient was admitted in the morning and provided with the Fitbit around 11 am, it's plausible that the device missed recording night sleep for that particular day.

Another challenge was the devices' power supply, referring to battery life and constant need for charging for wireless devices (thermometer, smart watch, oximeter, sphygmomanometer, smart scale) as well as the continuous power supply for wired devices (depth camera and central data collection hub). The issue that occurred during the pilot testing was that the clinician had to be mindful of the battery levels of each device, even when there was no patient inside the ward. Also, other healthcare professionals that have access of the ward might accidentally unplug the device, resulting in disturbance in data collection.

It is noteworthy that all data from the devices were successfully obtained, with the exception of some missing data from the Withings' scale, as will be demonstrated later. Furthermore, there were interruptions in the data collection from the Fitbit device, as one patient was disturbed and removed the device from time to time.

An important external factor is also the existence of adequate infrastructure for accommodating all the devices. The lack of infrastructure, such as data collection hubs and internet connection were identified also during the co-creation sessions. In practice, an extra hospital ward that was not previously used was equipped with all the monitoring devices, the data collection hub, and a modem for internet connectivity. This caused challenges for the attending clinicians as they ended up being responsible for monitoring one additional room without the corresponding increase in personnel.

While these factors are external to both clinicians and patients they are of great importance and should be considered in the design and deployment of the system/technologies as they can pose additional challenges to the clinicians and the patients.

Clinician experience and perception

One major challenge in the system adoption is the clinical benefit that clinicians believe the system can provide to the patients. It was evident from the co-creation session that the value of using technologies for continuous monitoring was neither clear nor obvious, and strong evidence needed

to be provided. In practice, the clinicians reported difficulty in engaging patients in research activities due to perceived lack of benefit and poor understanding of research objectives.

The perceived ease of use (comprising the mental and physical effort needed to perform the monitoring and utilize the provided information) is also reported in the literature as a major challenge for physicians. The clinicians were sceptical about the time required from them to interpret the provided information and translate it into valuable decisions.

Ease of use is well related to what is reported in the literature as productivity impact, which refers to the degree a system can enhance or diminish productivity. The participants in the co-creation session reported that they were afraid that technology could add an extra burden to their already overloaded working schedule.

Finally, ease of data access referring to all the information being easily accessible whenever and for whoever needs it. was also a central point of discussion during the co-creation session, with participants mentioning the importance of the collected information being available for all the relevant stakeholders, such as clinicians, patients, family members and informal caregivers.

Patient experience and perception

Turning to patient experience, a challenge identified in the literature is the user acceptance and engagement. Although pervasive technologies do not require active participation of the user, in practice there existed challenges recruiting and maintaining the patient in the study. The lack of motivation appeared to be causing frustration, leading to discontinuation of participation and difficulty in monitoring. Indeed, a negative attitude of the patient can be challenging to overcome, causing major impacts in on the clinical workflow.

This is why, despite the unobtrusive nature of technologies, recruiting and maintaining patient engagement posed significant challenges. The stress of having devices and undergoing daily measurements proved to be overwhelming for some patients, even in the clinical environment, intensifying their lack of motivation and leading to discontinuation of participation. This lack of motivation not only impacted patient involvement, but also resulted in one patient originally agreeing to participate and then being removed from the study. Additionally, it posed hurdles for clinicians in daily engagement and ensuring compliance with treatment and monitoring protocols. The overall reluctance or frustration to participate is further supported by the findings of the clinical assessment questionnaires.

The overall reluctance or frustration to participate is further supported by the findings of the clinical assessment questionnaires. More specifically, PHQ-9 results indicate a spectrum from lightly depressed to moderately depressed individuals, with scores ranging from 5 to 10 while MoCA average score was 22.6 out of 30, with a range of 16-26 that may indicate cognitive impairment to 4 out of 5 patients (Table 10).

Moreover, the SF-12 assessment tool (Table 10) evaluates the physical and mental health status of the patients. The highest PCS score was at 46.511, falling within the moderate to good range, while the lowest PCS score at 25.499, indicates poorer physical health outcomes. These scores suggest a varied spectrum of physical health statuses among the patients, with some experiencing better physical functioning and general health perception than others. The MCS scores are also ranging from the highest 48.639 which indicates moderate to good condition, to the lowest 34.7 which indicates a poor to fair mental condition. Low MCS scores may signal the need for psychosocial support, mental health screening, or interventions to address emotional distress. It's worth mentioning that individuals with higher psychometric scores proved to be the most collaborative ones. The patients with higher scores were more willing to participate in the study and this might indicate that the continuous monitoring was perceived as an extra burden for people that already experiencing some psychological or physical difficulties.

Furthermore, the lack of perceived control and interactivity (Poon et al., 2021), although at the beginning was perceived as beneficial, in practice it was reported as a major challenge to clinicians. It was difficult for the attending clinician to engage the patient daily and ensure compliance with treatment and monitoring protocols.

To better understand and validate our observations regarding the challenges related to patient mobility, we used the Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS), as well as the data extraction for the smart scale and Heel2Toe devices. For patients with low mobility, such as those with a Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS) score of 6 indicating moderate frailty, the process of measurement became even more challenging. Balancing and remaining still for several seconds, necessary for accurate measurements, caused serious discomfort even though the patient was physically able to perform the measurement.

The process of extracting sleep data from Fitbit devices also posed some challenges. As mentioned previously, we cannot be sure whether the patient wears or takes off the watch, as there is no such message from the Fitbit. Therefore, it ultimately comes down to the patient ensuring that they wear the device consistently for accurate tracking.

In a specific case, the ongoing acquisition of sleep data was unexpectedly disrupted due to a patient's discomfort, prompting them to remove the device. Additionally, variations in sleeping patterns might arise from the hospital environment itself, including disturbances and unfamiliar settings, contributing to discrepancies in sleep data. Figure 4 shows an example of the sleeping pattern for the patient which indicates interruptions in a sleep pattern. It is important to note that these data corresponds to the patient who expressed concern and frustration with wearing the Fitbit device, and therefore, the exact timing of device removal and reapplication is uncertain.

Week of Nov 27th, 2023		3 hrs 24 mins avg
11/28/2023	Tue 11 am - Tue 12 pm	1 hrs 3 mins
11/27/2023	Sun 6 pm - Mon 12 am	5 hrs 45 mins
Week of Nov 20th, 2023		3 hrs 25 mins avg
11/26/2023	Sun 2 pm - Sun 3 pm	1 hrs 44 mins
11/26/2023	Sun 10 am - Sun 1 pm	2 hrs 7 mins
11/26/2023	Sun 8 am - Sun 9 am	1 hrs 27 mins
11/25/2023	Sat 10 pm - Sat 11 pm	57 mins
11/25/2023	Sat 4 am - Sat 8 am	3 hrs 21 mins
11/24/2023	Fri 1 am - Fri 4 am	2 hrs 44 mins
11/23/2023	Thu 10 pm - Thu 11 pm	1 hrs 19 mins

Figure 4. Example of Sleeping Data from Fitbit

Moreover, one of the data collection challenges arose on the day of discharge when patients were asked to spend time in the Living Lab to complete a morning routine. However, it was apparent that upon discharge, patients were more inclined to quickly return home rather than spend much time in the Living Lab while wearing the Heel2Toe device. This was reflected on the average step count per patient, with a notably low step average of 49.2 steps, this emphasizes the necessity to better engage patients on their final day to ensure more active participation. Additionally, it is important to note that one patient did not wear the device, which is why data from only four patients are presented.

Table 12. Steps Data from Heel2Toe

Number of Steps	Number of satisfactory steps	Percentage of Satisfactory Steps (%)
143	127	88.81%

Number of Steps	Number of satisfactory steps	Percentage of Satisfactory Steps (%)
147	71	48.30%
40	34	85%
37	35	94.59%

However, the Mentrage camera, which required no active participation from the patients, did not cause any such issues. Its passive nature made it more acceptable and less “of a burden” for patients, proving the importance of considering the level of patient involvement when implementing technology in healthcare settings.

Discussion:

Workflow challenges related to the use of technology in hospital settings. We also propose certain actions to mitigate the issues that arise in practice. It is worth clarifying that our data refers to a system that is currently under development with clinical value and feasibility still in construction. Thus, our recommendations are mainly addressing the efficacy/feasibility of research studies in real-life, clinical environments like a hospital.

1. The use of monitoring devices requires extra time on the part of the attending clinician. It is important to identify the incentives for clinicians to participate in such endeavours. Although new personnel can be recruited to perform the research, the participation of the attending clinicians remains of utmost importance.
2. Implementation of such technologies requires additional skills that are not essential in daily clinical practice. The personnel training is crucial, and time should be allocated before starting the activities. Also, an open communication and information exchange channel between the attending physicians and the research and technical team can assist in addressing the issues that arise.
3. Throughout the patient hospitalization it is usual to move patients from one hospital clinic to another based on the patient’s needs. This can cause disruption in patient monitoring as there is no single reference point. Since sharing resources among hospital clinics is neither common practice nor fluid, better communication between different hospitals and clinics would be beneficial.
4. Patient frustration during hospitalization can be a major issue for the attending clinician. Developing strategies to engage patients’ adherence to the use of technologies can improve participation and compliance with monitoring protocols.
5. The patient recruitment revealed more challenges than the ones initially planned. Although the patients are hospitalized and are undergoing clinical examinations daily, adding more measurements that they are done for research purposes can be frustrating. Despite its primary function as a centre for healthcare delivery, the clinical setting is usually causing discomfort resulting in feelings of anxiety or unease among patients.

Some important findings from the systematic use of devices for patient monitoring in clinical environments, are summarised in the following X points:

1. The feasibility testing of devices in real settings can reveal challenges that cannot be identified during the testing simulation.
2. The devices that are not worn by the patients were better perceived.
3. Although continuous monitoring using wearable devices can yield many advantages, the researchers should consider that the continuity of monitoring and the data quality relies heavily on the patient’s engagement even when no interactivity is required.

2.3.4 Conclusions

The pilot study reveals significant challenges for deploying continuous patient monitoring technologies in real clinical settings. A key barrier identified is the perceived lack of value of such technology among both patients and clinicians, particularly when its clinical utility and feasibility are

still being explored. Thus, involving patients and clinicians in the research design process, following Living Lab principles, becomes essential for addressing these challenges and ensuring successful implementation.

Furthermore, it's crucial to integrate these technologies seamlessly into existing clinical workflows to prevent disruption. Providing comprehensive training and support to healthcare professionals can help alleviate resistance to change and promote widespread acceptance. Effective communication among healthcare professionals, researchers, and technical teams is paramount. Continuous incorporation of clinicians' feedback through an iterative design process is necessary. Additionally, exploring incentives for patients and healthcare provider participation is critical.

It's important to note that these findings are primarily applicable to the Greek healthcare system and may not directly translate to other global healthcare contexts due to distinct practices and characteristics. Moreover, the study's limitation, conducted in a single hospital with a limited number of participants, underscores the need for caution when extrapolating the results.

In conclusion, while pervasive technologies pose challenges in clinical practice, they offer significant potential for enhancing patient care and outcomes. By engaging patients and physicians in the research process, addressing concerns, and ensuring seamless integration into clinical workflows, these barriers can be effectively addressed and overcome.

2.4 Case Study 4. VITALEs: Digital-enhanced transitional care pilot for post-surgical patients (LifeSpace Living Lab UPM · Spain)

2.4.1 Small scale pilot study description

VITALEs (vitals in Spanish) is a study by LifeSpace Living Lab - UPM conducted as part of the VITALISE project in Madrid, Spain, aimed at gathering crucial data supporting transitional care, focusing on the period encompassing hospital discharge and home recovery. This small-scale pilot closely monitored 15 patients recuperating at home following hip or knee replacement surgeries. Its primary two objectives were:

- To evaluate the feasibility, efficacy and benefit of collecting multi-channel data utilising Internet of Things (IoT) devices to monitor the recovery progress of patients within their home environments and using LifeSpace Living Lab to harmonise data collection and processes.
- To investigate the collection and use of digital biomarkers + PROMs (subjective data) and explore initial patterns that could demonstrate the potential to predict transition outcomes, such as readmissions and adverse events.

This pilot has been carried out from the co-creation phase to the sharing of the data generated with the scientific community, going through all the typical phases of a pilot (see Figure 5). Different entities have been involved in the whole process, special mention to INTRAS Foundation that was in charge of carrying out and extracting the results of the co-creation sessions.

Figure 5. Transitional Care pilot at LifeSpace Living Lab phases

The preparation phase begins with the inclusion criteria definition (residents of Community of Madrid recovering from a recent knee or hip replacement surgery, with WiFi connection at home), and the preparation of materials, including the IoT kits pre-setting, an informational website (<https://vitalis.lst.tfo.upm.es/>), the user manuals and informed consents writing and printing. The IoT kit is composed by 4 IoT devices that were used and validated: thermometer, blood pressure monitor, pulse-oximeter and activity tracking smartwatch + smartphone connected to all devices and to the Living Lab cloud. Secondly, the recruitment was done in collaboration with Clínica Cemtro at *Escuela de Prótesis* (<https://www.clinicacentro.com/paciente/escuela-protesis-online/>), a master class held by a nurse for future patients of knee or hip replacement surgery, to help them prepare for the process early-on, including the transitional care at home, and clear any doubts. These classes are done monthly and attendance varies from 10 to 50 people. We presented the project in 10 of these sessions with an open invitation to participate reaching a total of 51 patients and recruiting 18 users.

During this phase, special attention is given to ethical and legal considerations: 1) before conducting the study, an application was submitted to the UPM ethical committee including participant recruitment, consent procedures, data collection, and potential risks to participants. Upon review, approval was obtained; 2) ensuring that participants provide informed consent before participating in the project, informing them about the project's goals, procedures, risks, and benefits, allowing them to make an informed decision about participation; 3) implementing measures to protect the privacy and security of participants' data collected through the IoT devices including encryption, secure storage practices, and limiting access to authorized personnel only.

The deployment phase covers an in-person visit to patients' homes (~1 week after surgery) to do the installation of IoT devices and a detailed instruction on their use, including the baseline assessment answering the initial questionnaires (sociodemographics –gender, date of birth, level of education–, EQ-5D-5L and open questions /expectations), and the training session performing a first –guided– measurement for day 1 of the study.

The running phase encompasses the next 14 days, where users were actively monitoring themselves using each IoT device once a day. This phase also includes addressing any issues encountered during monitoring promptly combining text messages, phone and video calls with patients directly.

D6.3 Summary of the performed activities for JRA2

Figure 6. Transitional Care small scale pilot study in Madrid outline

Finally, the assessment phase begins with a second in-person visit to patients' homes for final evaluation questionnaires (EQ-5D-5L, System Usability Scale, Technology Acceptance Measurement, IEXPAC and open questions/feedback) and removal of the IoT kit. This is followed by the integration and analysis of all patient data in an anonymised form (it is a feasibility study of the monitoring and data collecting process, therefore no personal data was processed). Once the different data sources are collected, the evaluation is performed and results are extracted.

2.4.2 Execution

2.4.2.1 Living Lab services

These Living Lab services guided the various phases of the VITALES pilot project, facilitating collaboration, innovation and iterative development to ultimately improve transitional care processes for patients recovering at home.

R&D SERVICES

- **Access to data:** provided datasets collected during the pilot for virtual access, focusing on data collected through the utilization of IoT devices and PROMs to foster the collaboration and innovation among researchers, healthcare professionals, and stakeholders.
- **Capacity building:** provide training to patients on the utilization of IoT devices for daily parameter collection thus patients are empowered to actively participate in regularly monitoring their vitals or health parameters.
- **Co-creation sessions:** gather information supporting the transitional care process, focusing on evaluating the feasibility, efficacy, and benefit of collecting multi-channel data to better understand the patients and healthcare professionals needs and preferences.
- **Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study:** developing a new digital-based solution for health monitoring because there was no tool available to collect the parameters defined in the study.
- **Impact assessment and validation test:** extract results from the pilot to assess its impact and validate it for facilitating evidence-based decision-making and the successful implementation of digital health solutions.
- **Legal, regulation and safety standard support:** applied to the UPM ethical committee, obtained approval, ensured informed consent from participants, and implemented measures

to protect data privacy and security to ensure compliance with ethical and regulatory requirements.

- **Prototyping test:** testing in a control environment prior piloting the VITALEs solution in a real-life setting to ensure functionality, usability, and reliability while minimizing risks associated with full-scale implementation.
- **Small-scale real life testing and experimentation:** executed the pilot to test the solution in a real-life setting, closely monitoring patients recovering at home following hip or knee replacement surgeries. It facilitates the validation in real-world scenarios, the evaluation of the patients experience and the identification of implementation hurdles.

BACK-OFFICE SERVICES

- **Data analysis:** provide comprehensive analysis, data analysis techniques, quality assurance and interpretation for extracting meaningful insights and understand the pilot benefits.
- **Data anonymization and pseudonymization:** pseudonymize patients' data through an ID to ensure that sensitive data collected during the Transitional Care pilot study is protected.
- **Dissemination:** communicate and share information with healthcare professionals and patients through a dedicated website, leaflets/brochures and in-person awareness events to effectively raise awareness about the pilot study in transitional care, engage stakeholders, and maximize participation and impact.
- **Ethical application preparation:** applied to the UPM ethical committee: study protocol and other forms in order to streamline the process, enhance compliance with ethical standards, and facilitate the approval of a case study involving human participants.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** co-creation: engaged 3 patients, 2 carers, and 7 health professionals; pilot execution: reached out to a total of 51 patients and recruited 18 users through a private health clinic.

2.4.2.2 Technical solution

The implementation strategy within the VITALISE project has underscored the critical importance of leveraging advanced technology available in LifeSpace Living Lab to expedite the integration process, ensuring the interoperability of all its components (see Figure 7). Collaborating with leading manufacturers, such as *Fitbit* and *Withings*, who provide their own REST APIs for data collection, has facilitated the centralization of this data on our servers, allowing for deeper analysis and broader application of the findings.

Figure 7. LifeSpace Transitional Care pilot - conceptual technical solution

Detailed Data Integration Process Explanation

- **Sensors/Actuators:** The frontline elements in data collection, equipped with wireless communication technologies like Bluetooth or WiFi. These devices range from wearables (activity trackers, wristbands) to on-demand devices (scales, thermometers, pulse oximeters), transmitting the collected data directly to the gateway. This initial phase is crucial for the effective and accurate capture of health and wellness information.
- **Gateway:** An Android-operating mobile device with the manufacturers' mobile apps installed. It uses Bluetooth and WiFi not only to receive data from the sensors/actuators but also to upload this information to the manufacturers' cloud using mobile connectivity. The gateway acts as an essential intermediary in the data transmission process.
- **Manufacturer Cloud:** Data centres of the device manufacturers, where all the data sent by the gateway is stored. These platforms offer dashboards, analysis, and insights, along with a REST API for programmatic data retrieval. Their role is to temporarily store the data before its final integration.
- **Bridge:** Given the diversity of APIs provided by manufacturers, utilising a unifying bridge like FitnessSyncer becomes essential. It collects and harmonises data from various manufacturers' clouds to store it in the LifeSpace Cloud. FitnessSyncer, supporting numerous APIs from common manufacturers, facilitates data integration onto a single platform.
- **LifeSpace Cloud:** The final destination for the generated data, stored on the LifeSpace environment's infrastructure. This cloud provides a REST API for programmatic access and data retrieval, ensuring its interoperability and the potential for integration with future system components.

IoT Devices Composition

This selection of devices reflects our commitment to capturing accurate and relevant data. Each device was chosen for its reliability, ease of use, and capability to integrate into our data architecture, ensuring cohesive and efficient data collection.

Table 13. IoT devices composition

Device	Model	Type of data
Pulseoximeter	Medisana PM 100 Connect	Oxygen blood level. SpO2
Thermometer	Withings Thermo	Smart Temporal Thermometer (Body Temperature)
Blood pressure monitor	Withings Connect BPM	Smart Wi-Fi blood pressure & heart rate monitor (arm cuff)
Activity wristband	Fitbit Charge 4	Smartwatch sensor- Gait features including steps, velocity, average distance

Integration of Data and Standardised Questionnaires

Special attention has been dedicated to integrating data collected through standardised questionnaires (EQ-5D-5L, IEXPAC, PAM, SUS, TAM, and sociodemographic information) alongside the technological infrastructure. This combination of biometric data from IoT devices and responses from standardised questionnaires offers a comprehensive view, facilitating a nuanced analysis of how technological interventions influence user experience and the overall quality of transitional care. By amalgamating these diverse data sets, we provide a holistic insight into the effectiveness of care strategies, underscoring the critical role of direct feedback and biometric monitoring in healthcare innovation.

Interoperability Achieved Through FHIR

A pivotal achievement within our case study is the ensured interoperability of collected data, achieved by employing the FHIR server within the LifeSpace Cloud. Initially, data was collected in its raw form from both IoT devices and the standardised questionnaires. To transform this raw data into a format that aligns with global health data standards, a bespoke software connector component was developed. This component is tasked with reading the raw data, translating it into FHIR resources, and subsequently publishing these resources on the LifeSpace Cloud's FHIR server. Storing the data on the FHIR server guarantees that the information remains consistent, secure, and accessible across diverse health systems and applications. Utilising FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) standards ensures that the collected data can be seamlessly shared and utilised, facilitating straightforward integration into both existing and future healthcare frameworks. This approach not only underscores the versatility and utility of FHIR in promoting data interoperability but also highlights our commitment to leveraging cutting-edge technology to enhance healthcare delivery.

2.4.3 Outcomes and Analysis

2.4.3.1 Co-creation phase

In Spain, three patients, two caregivers, and seven healthcare professionals participated in collaborative sessions adopting a person-centered approach. These sessions aimed to explore the utilization of ICT tools for gathering information to support the transitional care process, encompassing hospital discharge and recovery at home. They also sought to gather insights into current practices in transitional care, specifically from hospital to home.

The sessions comprised two segments, one involving patients and caregivers, and the other involving healthcare professionals, with the goal of comprehending diverse perspectives and enhancing contributions. Two experienced facilitators guided these inclusive sessions, ensuring equitable participation for all attendees. The sessions were structured into four blocks as shown in Figure 8:

Figure 8. Co-creation phase - discussion blocks

Key findings from the sessions included the participants' emphasis on the necessity for a protocol governing the transition process, which is currently lacking and often contingent on chance. While acknowledging the benefits provided by the healthcare system, participants expressed dissatisfaction with organizational structures and certain practices. Regarding technology, there was general acceptance among patients and caregivers, provided it complements rather than replaces human care. In contrast, healthcare professionals, accustomed to integrating technology into their daily routines, possessed a broader understanding of its impact on patient experiences and its acceptability. They leveraged technology not only to enhance individual care but also to streamline data collection processes.

Overall, the consensus was that digital technologies are welcome in integrated and transitional care processes, as long as they are tailored to the needs of users rather than imposing new requirements on them.

2.4.3.2 Methodology

The data collection process was focused on collecting several key performance indicators (KPIs) at two different points in time: the initial phase and the endpoint as shown in Table 14.

Initial Data Collection

- **Sociodemographic:** This included the collection of basic demographic information such as gender, date of birth, and level of education. This data was important to understand the composition of the participant pool.
- **EQ-5D-5L:** This is a standardized instrument developed by the EuroQol Group to measure health-related quality of life. It consists of 5 dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression, each of which has 5 levels of severity. This tool was used at the initial phase to assess the baseline health status of participants (right after the surgery).
- **Open Questions (Expectations):** This qualitative measure involved asking participants about their expectations regarding the VITALEs study they will be experiencing. Open-ended questions provided us rich, descriptive data to improve the process.

Endpoint Data Collection

- **EQ-5D-5L (Again):** Repeating this measure at the endpoint allowed us to compare participants' health-related quality of life before and after the VITALEs intervention.
- **System Usability Scale (SUS):** This is a simple, ten-item scale giving a global view of subjective assessments of usability. It allowed us to evaluate how user-friendly a system was, which was crucial for any interventions involving technology or new processes.
- **Technology Acceptance Measurement (TAM):** This assessment measures how participants accept and intend to use technology based on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. It was useful for evaluating the adoption of new technologies.

- **IEXPAC:** This stands for the Instrument to Evaluate the EXperience of PATients with Chronic diseases. It's a tool to measure the experience of care for patients with chronic conditions. We adapted for the case of VITALES that participants were under surgery process.
- **Open Questions (Feedback):** At the endpoint, these open-ended questions were aimed at understanding participants' feedback on the intervention. It was an opportunity for participants to express their views on what worked well and what could be improved.

Table 14. KPIs collected in each phase of VITALES study

Initial	End point
Sociodemographic (Including gender, date of birth, level of education)	EQ-5D-5L
EQ-5D-5L	System Usability Scale
Open questions (expectations)	Technology Acceptance Measurement
	IEXPAC
	Open questions (feedback)

The materials from the analysis of the data collected through the VITALES pilot are as follows:

The programming environments used have been Python and R implementing the usual libraries, *pandas* for data manipulation and cleaning, *numpy* for numerical operations, *matplotlib* and *seaborn* for data visualization. The questionnaires have been analyzed using the statistical methods that each of them implements since they are validated questionnaires. And for the particular case of the EQ5-5D-5L they have been done with the "Paretian Classification of Health Change" (PCHC) is a method for classifying changes in the health of individuals based on the Pareto principle. In the context of the EQ-5D health-related quality of life instrument, PCHC could be used to classify individuals' health transitions between two time points (e.g., before and after an intervention), which are the PreStudy and PostStudy measurements.

2.4.3.3 Data analysis

Sociodemographic

The pilot study initially recruited 18 participants. However, only 10 participants completed the pilot, indicating that there were 8 dropouts due to several reasons (not interested anymore, not feeling comfortable, pain after surgery, etc.). The participants were divided by gender and the type of intervention they received (either hip or knee). The mean age of male participants is listed as 65.33 years with a standard deviation (SD) of 7.09 years. The mean age of female participants is slightly higher at 69.29 years with a larger SD of 10.00 years. Regarding the types of interventions, participants who received a hip intervention have a mean age of 70.00 years with an SD of 11.75 years. Participants who received a knee intervention are younger on average, with a mean age of 66.83 years and an SD of 7.68 years. As a result, 6 participants were under knee surgery and 4 participants were under hip surgery.

Table 15. Participants age-gender relations

Gender	Mean age	Age SD
Male	65.33 years	7.09

Gender	Mean age	Age SD
Female	69.29 years	10.00

Technology Acceptance Measurement (TAM)

Table 16 presents the results from the Technology Acceptance Measurement (TAM) questionnaire, which assessed participants' acceptance of a "VITALES monitoring kit." The TAM model was used to evaluate how users come to accept and use a technology: User Acceptance (UA), Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU). As a result, we obtained the following:

Perceived Use (PU): The statement "Using the VITALES monitoring kit could help me perform my activities more quickly" has a mean score of 3.7 with an SD of 1.57, indicating moderate agreement with some variability in responses. "Using the VITALES monitoring kit could help me" has a mean score of 3.8 with an SD of 1.03, suggesting a slightly higher level of agreement with less variability among participants.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEU): Participants strongly agree (mean score of 4.3) that they could easily learn to use the VITALES monitoring kit, with an SD of 0.95, which suggests that most participants found the system easy to learn. The statement about it being a good idea to use the kit for a full and safe recovery has a mean score of 3.8 and an SD of 1.23, indicating moderate agreement but with more variability than the ease of learning.

User Acceptance (UA): The statement about the VITALES monitoring kit involving significant changes in the current way of doing things has a mean score of 3.2 and an SD of 1.48, which is the lowest score among the statements and has high variability, indicating some reluctance or perceived difficulty in changing routines. The comfort with information and communication technologies scores a mean of 3.5 with an SD of 1.08, showing moderate agreement.

The overall means (with their respective SDs) for PU, PEU, and UA are 3.75 (1.16), 4.05 (0.96), and 3.35 (0.94) respectively. These results suggest that while there's a general positive perception towards the VITALES monitoring kit, there is a significant spread in responses, especially concerning the potential changes to current practices and routines.

Table 16. TAM results

Question		Mean	SD	Total – Mean (SD)
Perceived use (PU)	Using the VITALES monitoring kit could help me perform my activities more quickly	3.7	1.57	3.75 (1.16)
	Using the VITALES monitoring kit could help me	3.8	1.03	
Perceived ease of use (PEU)	I believe I could easily learn to use the VITALES monitoring kit	4.3	0.95	4.05 (0.96)
	I think it's a good idea to use the VITALES monitoring kit for a full and safe recovery	3.8	1.23	
User acceptance (UA)	Using the VITALES monitoring kit may involve significant changes in my current way of doing things	3.2	1.48	3.35 (0.94)

Question	Mean	SD	Total – Mean (SD)
I am comfortable with information and communication technologies	3.5	1.08	

System Usability Scale (SUS)

Figure 9 presents the theory behind the SUS questionnaire in order to understand the results

Figure 9. How to interpret the System Usability Scale (Gimeno Artigas, 2018)

Table 17 shown the results. The average SUS score is 64.17 out of 100. This score gave a general idea of how users perceive the usability of the system. The median value is 62.5, which indicates that half of the respondents rated the usability of the system as 62.5 or higher. The SD is 20.17, which is relatively high, indicating that there is considerable variability in how users rated the system. The system has been rated as "OK," which suggests that users found the usability to be average or acceptable. Finally, the system has been assigned a grade of C, indicating a satisfactory but not outstanding usability score.

Table 17. SUS results from VITALEs study

SUS Study Score	64.17
Median	62.5
Standard Dev (SD)	20.17
Adjective	OK
Grade	C

Figure 10. SUS questions chart

The radar chart (Figure 10) provides a visual representation of the scores for individual questions on the SUS questionnaire, with each axis representing a question and the plotted values indicating the scores. All the values seem to range between 4 and 8 on the 0-10 scale, suggesting that no single aspect of usability was rated as extremely poor or excellent by most users.

The results indicate that the system is considered moderately usable, with some room for improvement. The wide range of responses implies that while some participants of the study found the system quite usable, others encountered some issues (probably due to the technology literacy).

Experience of chronic patient: IEXPAC

This scale is called IEXPAC (Instrument for the Evaluation of the eXperience of Chronic Patient). IEXPAC is oriented to the improvement of outcomes, both clinical and those relevant to the person. It is a scale of 11+4 items that, in a simple, direct and quick way, responds to the need of health and social organizations to incorporate the experience of patients in order to transform the care model and obtain better results (for patients and for the organization).

According to Figure 11, we can interpret the following results per category:

- **Needs & Preferences:** This category has the highest average score, suggesting that the VITALEs Monitoring Kit aligns well with the needs and preferences of the users.
- **Wellbeing & Life Quality:** Also scores highly, indicating that users feel the device has a positive impact on their wellbeing and quality of life.
- **Usage Information:** Receives a slightly lower score than the top categories but still indicates that users feel well-informed about how to use the device.
- **Confidence & Autonomy:** This category has a moderate score, suggesting that the device moderately contributes to users' confidence and autonomy.
- **Functionality Review and Recovery Objectives:** Both receive moderate scores, implying that users find the functionality of the device to be adequate and feel that it somewhat meets their recovery objectives.
- **Internet & Mobile Use:** This has a similar score to Recovery Objectives, indicating that the internet and mobile aspects of the kit are considered to be reasonably satisfactory.
- **Device Review:** Has a moderate score, suggesting an overall satisfactory impression of the devices and kit but with room for improvement.
- **Quality of Life Concern:** This receives a score that indicates users see some advantages to quality of life when using the device, but not as strongly as other categories.

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- **Device Advantages:** Has a moderate to low score, which may suggest that while there are some perceived benefits, they are not outstanding.
- **Experience Sharing:** This has one of the lower scores, indicating that users might not find sharing their experiences with the device as easy or beneficial.
- **Post-Hospital Care:** Also scores low, suggesting that the device's role in post-hospital care might not be meeting user expectations.
- **Problem Solving:** This has the lowest score, indicating that the device may be least effective in solving problems for the users.

Figure 11. Results from IEXPAC

Quality of Life: EQ5-5D-5L

The Figure 12 represents the results from the EQ-5D-5L questionnaire, which is a tool for assessing health-related quality of life across five dimensions: Mobility (MO), Self-Care (SC), Usual Activities (UA), Pain/Discomfort (PD), and Anxiety/Depression (AD). The EQ-5D-5L allowed participants to rate their level of difficulty in each dimension on a scale from 1 (no problems) to 5 (extreme problems) at the two main points of the VITALEs study, before and after an intervention. The height of each bar indicates the percentage of respondents who gave a particular score in a dimension.

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Figure 12. EQ-5D-5L results from VITALES study: Pre-post comparison

In the PreStudy phase, the majority of respondents report some problems (score of 3, in green) with MO, UA, PD. AD show more variability, with higher percentages of respondents experiencing moderate to low problems (scores of 1 in red).

In the PostStudy phase, there seems to be an overall shift towards higher scores (less problems) in MO, UA and PD compared to the PreStudy phase. This suggests a potential improvement in these dimensions. AD also show variability, with a significant portion of respondents indicating low to moderate anxiety.

It's notable that there is a slight enhancement in problems reported in the PostStudy phase for MO, SC and UA, which might indicate that the VITALES intervention improve the respondents' perceived abilities in these areas. There may also be an increase in higher scores (greater problems) in the dimensions of PD, and AD post-study, suggesting a slightly enhancement in perceived health-related quality of life.

Finally, according to Figure 13, we can state that:

Figure 13. Comparison of the Health Status by Group

- **PreStudy:** The distribution of health ratings before the study starts with a wider range at the lower end, indicating that a significant number of participants rated their health lower. The median rating appears to be around 7, and the density of the plot suggests that most ratings are between 6 and 8. The 'tail' of the plot extends towards the lower ratings, which means that there are some ratings of poorer health, but these are less frequent.
- **PostStudy:** The distribution after the study shows a more consistent range of health ratings around a central median, which also appears to be around 7. There's less variability in the data compared to the PreStudy group, as indicated by the narrower 'tails' of the violin plot. This suggests that participants' health ratings became more consistent after the study, with fewer low ratings.

Comparing the two groups, the health status ratings seem relatively stable in terms of the median value from PreStudy to PostStudy. However, the distribution of ratings in the PreStudy group is more varied, with a significant portion of participants rating their health status lower. In contrast, the PostStudy group shows a tighter distribution with less variability, suggesting that the VITALEs intervention or circumstances during the study may have led to more consistency in how participants rated their health status.

2.4.4 Conclusions

The VITALEs pilot conducted by UPM at LifeSpace Living Lab has been a study aimed at researching transitional care focusing on the hospital-to-home care process. Designing, developing, and implementing such a study to validate an innovative technological solution in preventing potential accidents or injuries during hip and knee interventions in the recovery process posed significant technical, technological, implementation, and scientific challenges. This journey now enables us to identify several barriers, lessons learned, and future lines of work for LifeSpace Living Lab to be continue consolidating its commitment in the field of health, care, and healthcare.

Addressing the challenge of collecting and unifying raw data from diverse IoT devices into a single cloud was overcome by implementing a custom software connector and FHIR standards, offering valuable lessons in interoperability and technology integration.

Inviting external healthcare institutions to participate in a project for piloting with users/patients with specific cases is always a challenge, at times functioning as a barrier. Additionally, due to the nature of the project, the difficult to offer any gratification or incentive for participation posed an extra barrier to recruitment and adherence.

The fear and apprehension of recruited users to participate in the pilot acted as a barrier in some cases but also as a driving force for interest in the solution being validated in the pilot in many others. It is also important to note that simultaneous technical-technological development alongside

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recruitment required significant effort to keep users engaged until the solution was ready for deployment. Detailed planning was therefore necessary and considered fundamental for these pilots.

Communication and awareness materials, generally considered a supportive tool, have been a key piece for institutional enrolment and the empowerment of patients. Home visits, educational attention regarding technologies, and personalized care through a telephone helpline were differentiating elements to provide support from the beginning to the end of the intervention. This highlights the importance of having a team in the Living Lab that can guarantee this commitment to user care for the success of any pilot. All of this added an important extra burden to be considered for other studies of this nature.

Detailed information regarding safety and ethics presented a challenge at the beginning of the project to find the best tools and messages to transparently convey the process and build trust. Investing time in this exercise prior to the start of the pilot allowed us to consolidate our differential position to be capable of conveying security and encouragement to potential users.

The results obtained in the pilot are encouraging and motivate us to continue working towards refinement and improvement, in order to advance its development and evolution for testing over longer periods.

3 Harmonized Analysis across Living Labs in Transitional Care

This study, conducted as part of VITALISE that focused on the harmonization of Living Labs procedures, explores transitional care. The research aims to assess the feasibility and benefits of multi-channel data collection in Living Labs, with the goal of harmonizing processes and data collection. In addition, it aims to investigate the collection and use of digital biomarkers to potentially predict transition outcomes such as readmissions and adverse events.

The research protocol outlines a prospective, multicenter, observational cohort study divided into three phases: co-creation, testing and simulation, and a cross-national pilot. The co-creation phase aims to establish a common baseline across centers and explore variations in discharge management between countries. The testing and simulation phase deepens the integration of patient clinical status observation, patient engagement and discharge education. Meanwhile, the transnational pilot phase tests the activities designed in the previous phases, collecting data for initial predictive analysis. Ultimately, this research aims to establish harmonized procedures and data collection methodologies across Living Labs to support transitions in care. Furthermore, it aims to improve Big Data analytics capabilities, considering local contexts within and across Living Labs.

3.1 Living Lab harmonized services

The essence of involving Living Labs services in innovation processes, and especially in the healthcare sector, lies in their capacity to foster an inclusive and harmonized atmosphere where user-centric innovation extends beyond addressing end-user needs. Healthcare innovation must demonstrate flexibility and feasibility in real-world testing while accommodating the diverse requirements of multiple stakeholders. Living Lab approaches allow to navigate strict **regulatory frameworks** and optimize limited resources, ensuring the design and implementation of healthcare innovations that not only meet regulatory standards but also align with clinical practices and protocols. The harmonization of **regulatory aspects**, clinical requirements and protocols along with human factors and uncontrolled environments is particularly necessary in transitional care settings, where addressing the dynamic challenges inherent in the in-hospital and out-of-hospital processes requires highly adaptive methodologies. Living Lab services provide a structured framework for navigating the complicated landscape of transitional care, enabling healthcare innovations to undergo rigorous **real-world testing** while remaining adaptable to the diverse requirements of varying networks of stakeholders involved.

Central to this process are **capacity building** initiatives and **co-creation sessions**, which serve as cornerstones for engaging and empowering diverse stakeholders within the transitional care ecosystem. By bringing together patients, healthcare providers, and researchers/technologists, these Living Lab services facilitate the exchange of knowledge and ideas, fostering a collaborative spirit crucial for iterative solution development. In the context of transitional care, where patients navigate the complex path of rehabilitation and reintegration into daily life after a hospital stay, there is an opportunity for impactful innovation. These are contexts where patients may need to relearn about their habits, for example due to reduced mobility, and in that evolution, there are clear needs for independence, safety, empowerment, and engagement with their treatment, all of which are key factors in the Living Labs approach. In addition to the **active involvement** of new stakeholders, including caregivers and family members.

Moreover, **simulation tests** and **small-scale real-life testing and experimentation** play a pivotal role in evaluating the efficacy and impact of healthcare innovations within the context of transitional care. These testing phases provide invaluable insights into the practical implementation of interventions, allowing for refinement to address the specific needs and challenges faced by patients and health professionals.

In terms of **data collection**, Living Lab methodologies offer a comprehensive approach to analyzing health trajectories, combining quantitative and qualitative data, including biomarkers and user experience metrics, such as usability and acceptance. This holistic approach enhances our understanding of the transitional care process to potentially develop solutions to predict critical outcomes such as readmissions and adverse events, essential metrics for the success of transitional

care models. Additionally, the integration of **legal, regulatory, and safety standards** preparation within Living Labs ensures adherence to the highest levels of data protection and patient safety throughout the innovation process to the full-scale implementation, further enhancing the credibility and reliability of transitional care interventions.

3.2 JRA2 Comparative results and challenges

3.2.1 Challenges and current practices in technology use for data collection

The integration of technology into the transitional care data collection process is of interest in improving these in-hospital and out-of-hospital processes (post-discharge process). However, from the different co-creation sessions held in the different pilots described above, we found several challenges common to all of them. At the core of these challenges is the **lack of resources**, which manifests itself as an obstacle to acquiring and maintaining the necessary technological infrastructure, such as computers, mobile devices, IoT devices, wearables and software systems such as electronic health records (EHRs) and data analysis tools. This shortage is especially pronounced in rural areas, where **financial constraints** are most severe. Added to this, there is the problem of **information fragmentation**: as patients move from one care facility to another, crucial details about their medical history, treatment plans and medication records are often lost due to the absence of a unified data exchange system. This fragmentation leaves healthcare professionals without the overview needed to make well-informed decisions. The **technology breach** is another major challenge that is further exacerbated by the lack of digital literacy of both healthcare professionals and patients. For healthcare professionals, the steep learning curve associated with new technologies can lead to resistance to change, while patients, especially those who are elderly or from less favored circumstances, may find it difficult to participate effectively in their care due to misunderstandings or the inability to access their health information. **Trust** issues further aggravate these challenges; concerns about privacy, data security and consent create doubts among both patients and healthcare staff, thereby potentially hindering the benefits of digital tools in transitional care. In the context of these challenges, current practices are apparently evolving to take advantage of the potential of technology to improve care transitions, as described in the results of the co-creation sessions. Investments in digital infrastructure are becoming more common, focusing on acquiring the necessary hardware and developing secure, easy-to-use software solutions. They also try to put effort into improving the **interoperability** of EHR systems by developing standards and frameworks, in order to reduce information silos and ensure continuity of care, however, this is still a problem today. In several of the sites interviewed, education and training programs are being put in place to bridge the digital gap, targeting both healthcare professionals and patients, in order to improve their skills in the use of digital tools and their understanding of the principles of **data privacy and security**. In addition, it is recognized that building trust through transparency and **engagement** is critical; clear communication about data collection, use and protection, along with the involvement of patients and healthcare professionals in the development and implementation of technology solutions, is essential to foster **acceptance** and optimize the use of technology in transitional care.

3.2.2 Common devices and measurements

Regarding the devices and metrics for each pilot, Table 19 shows the individual (and common analysis, highlighted in green) indicating a joint effort to standardize these metrics for transitional care across country. In terms of devices, the Fitbit Charge 4/5, used in AUTH, MCGILL and UPM, stands out, this being the focus for consistent activity and health tracking. Likewise, for the collection of digital biomarkers, smart devices such as blood pressure, thermometer, or walking sensor have been used and shared in at least 2 pilot sites. In terms of PROMs and PREMs, there appears to be a consistent application of standardized scales such as the EuroQoL Health Status Scale and the System Usability Scale (SUS) across almost all pilot sites, indicating an emphasis on assessing the quality of life and usability of transitional care from the patient's perspective. While there are shared methodologies in patient experience and device data collection, each pilot has wisely adapted other instruments according to the study design (see JRAs protocols submitted).

Table 18. JRA2 devices and PROMs/PREMs overview

	LAUREA	MCGILL	AUTH	UPM
PROMs/PREMs	N/A	EQ-5D-3L (Health status)	EuroQol (EQ-5D-5L)	EuroQol (EQ-5D-5L)
		PROMIS 29 (Health-related quality of life)	12-Item Short Form Survey (SF-12)	System Usability Scale (SUS)
		System Usability Scale (SUS)	Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)	Technology acceptance measurement (TAM)
			Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living Scale (Lawton IADL)	
			International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ-short)	
			MONTREAL COGNITIVE ASSESSMENT (MoCA)	
			Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS)	
			Charlson Comorbidity Index	
DEVICES	Simulation manikins (Gaumard/Laerdal)	Fitbit Charge 5	Fitbit Charge 5	Fitbit Charge 4
	Nordic simulator recording system	Insoles sensor (Physio Biometrics walking sensor)	3D depth sensors (MentorAge)	Pulse oximeter Medisana PM 100 Connect
	Pan-tilt-zoom cameras	Automatic upper arm blood pressure monitor	Smart scale (Withings Body+)	Thermometer Withings Thermo
	Logitech conference camera		Thermometer	Blood Pressure Monitor Withings BPM Connect
	GoPro Max camera		Insoles sensor (Physio Biometrics walking sensor)	
	Microphone		Automatic upper arm blood pressure monitor	

Legend = green means commonality across pilot sites

3.3 Economic impact assessment

The aim of this section is to perform an economic impact assessment examining the **feasibility and benefit** of collecting multichannel data across Living Labs on the topic of transitional care (JRA2) as well as **assess the economic impact** of utilizing lower-cost home monitoring devices compared to more expensive clinical setting monitoring tools. Each of such activities seeks to examine and illuminate the requirements as well as challenges regarding transitions of patients from the hospital to the home care thereby providing invaluable insights into improving the practice of transition care. These case studies aim to thoroughly examine transition needs for patients by using different geographical and health contexts.

The performed small scale case studies involved deploying IoT devices and digital infrastructure, stimulating economic activity through **equipment, software, and service purchases**. Deployment and operation likely **generated jobs** in healthcare technology, data analysis, and project management. While not directly impacting spending, the findings could lead to **improved transitional care**, potentially **reducing costs associated with readmissions and complications**.

Effective transitional care programs have been shown to significantly reduce hospital readmission rates (Fønss Rasmussen et al., 2021). The JRA2's pilot studies focus on continuous patient monitoring aims to achieve this by providing real-time data to healthcare professionals, **optimizing post-discharge care decisions**, and ultimately leading to cost savings for healthcare system through the use of IoT devices for effective care. For readers ease indicatively the occurred costs of such devices are provided in the table below:

Table 19. IoT devices costs

IoT Device	Price
Medisana PM 100 Connect	~ 40 euros
Withings Thermo	~ 100 euros
Withings BPM Connect	~ 130 euros
Fitbit Charge 4	~ 130 euros

Home monitoring allows patients to monitor their health parameters in the comfort of their own homes, **eliminating the need to travel to a clinical setting**. This convenience can lead to better adherence to monitoring schedules and overall improved health outcomes. While clinical setting monitoring may provide more accurate and immediate results due to professional oversight, home monitoring devices have significantly improved in accuracy over the years (THINRS Executive Committee and Site Investigators et al., 2016). Many home monitoring devices are now designed to provide reliable results that are comparable to clinical settings.

Furthermore, by collecting real-time data, the case studies aimed to streamline transitional care processes. This efficiency translates to **potential cost savings for providers and insurers**, along with **improved patient outcomes**. Monitoring could **free up time for caregivers**, allowing them to return to work sooner or reduce reliance on paid home care. Better home monitoring and management could lead to **faster healing, fewer complications, and improved long-term health**, potentially saving costs due to **reduced need** for additional healthcare services.

In the VITALEs study, patient well-being improved with the VITALEs kit which improves patient satisfaction, as shown by high scores in specific quality-of-life and needs/preferences categories. This suggests the kit and home devices in general align well with patient preferences and foster a

better quality of life. Additionally, increased patient satisfaction may lead to **better adherence to treatment plans**, potentially **lowering healthcare costs in the long run**.

Apart from patient satisfaction, the pilot studies performed foster technology innovation which has a key economic impact both on the healthcare providers and patients. The VITALEs pilot study contributes to healthcare innovation, particularly in **remote patient monitoring** and **digital health solutions**. These innovations could lead to **broader economic benefits** like **job creation, exports, and productivity gains**. Analyzing data from IoT devices requires robust data infrastructure and analytics. Investment in this infrastructure can have long-term economic benefits by **supporting innovation and competitiveness** in related industries.

Real-time monitoring of patient recovery aims to improve patient outcomes and quality of life by monitoring health indicators in vulnerable persons. Better health outcomes **indirectly benefit the economy through increased productivity and reduced absenteeism**. Early identification of potential complications or readmissions could **lessen the strain** on healthcare systems, **freeing up resources** for other needs. Although not a direct economic benefit, digital health technologies can contribute to the **environment** by reducing the need for physical appointments and transportation, leading to **lower carbon emissions**.

Apart from the case studies dedicated to user experience, case study 1 (LAUREA) is **future-oriented** and focuses on potential cost savings through improved patient care by better-trained nurses, focusing on education of future nurses for improved patient care. Simulation-based research (LAUREA) is indirect and focused on future cost savings rather than immediate financial benefits. While not directly affecting current healthcare costs, it can lead to better-prepared nurses in the future. Well-trained nurses who understand the importance of patient-centered care can potentially reduce complications, medication errors, and readmissions, ultimately leading to cost savings.

Overall, the economic impact of innovative IoT technologies in transitional care is multifaceted, with the potential to drive efficiency, improve outcomes, and create new opportunities for economic growth within the healthcare industry. By embracing and leveraging these advancements, healthcare systems can not only enhance patient care but also optimize resource utilization and foster innovation in the field of transitional care. Lastly, it should be stressed that the current study can serve as a reference point for reflection amongst the policy makers and facilitate the related public dialogue for future law making that would enhance the public healthcare systems of EU countries and reduce the occurred costs.

4 Recommendations for Transitional Care

In **clinical settings**, it is key that medical staff receive comprehensive training focused on the adoption and efficient use of new technologies such as wearable devices, smart devices and/or sensors. This training should highlight the benefits and demonstrate how these technologies can be seamlessly incorporated into everyday clinical practices, thereby encouraging greater acceptance and facilitating a smoother transition by also increasing technology skills and literacy. In addition, involving both patients and clinicians during the initial design and development phases of the studies protocols ensures that the technologies implemented are more closely aligned with real needs, thereby improving usability and perceived value. In the area of **home monitoring**, the use of strategies such as home visits, technology education sessions and the provision of a dedicated telephone support line play a key role in engaging and supporting patients during home interventions. These strategies help mitigate the anxiety associated with adopting new technologies by ensuring ongoing support. Equally important is overcoming technical barriers related to the interoperability of home monitoring devices and the successful transmission of data to providers. The adoption of standards such as FHIR significantly facilitates data exchange and utilization, improving patient care.

In addressing the challenges related to **comparability and applicability**, it is essential to establish uniform protocols for data collection and analysis across monitoring devices (which we did in VITALISE across the 3 JRAs). This ensures that the information obtained is consistent, comparable and useful for decision making. In this context, conducting similar pilot studies in different settings and countries helps us to validate the results and ensure that the knowledge gained is applicable in different contexts, thus overcoming the specificity of the studies to be determined. Finally, by focusing on **mobility monitoring and analysis and patient management**, the integration of technologies capable of assessing a patient's gait, stability and strength in both clinical and home settings is key to obtaining valuable information about a patient's recovery process, such as after surgical interventions, hip and knee replacements (the UPM pilot case) and stroke rehabilitation (the McGill pilot case). These systems must be easy to use for both patients and healthcare professionals and allow easy access to personalized treatment plans and progress monitoring. It is essential to establish a feedback loop to obtain continuous information on the usefulness and experience of using the technologies for transitional care management.

5 Conclusions

The JRA2 study provides insight into transitional care practices, with a particular focus on harmonizing data collection procedures and methods in Living Labs. Living Labs provide an integrative environment for user-centered healthcare innovation that accommodates the needs of diverse stakeholders while navigating regulatory frameworks and optimizing resources. The feasibility and advantages of multi-channel data collection within Living Labs to standardize processes and predict outcomes such as readmissions and adverse events has been explored.

Challenges such as resource limitations, information fragmentation, and digital literacy barriers have been identified. Future research and application efforts will need to address these challenges by investing in digital infrastructure, improving the interoperability health data, as well as providing education and training programs for healthcare professionals and patients on how they should handle digital tools properly.

Devices and metrics harmonization efforts have been started so future studies can build on these efforts and improve them. Economic impact on using IoT devices and home monitoring for transitional care processes could stimulate economic activity, which could translate into improved transitional care practices, reduced readmission rates, cost savings, and job creation in the tech sectors. Provided recommendations for transitional care include training health professionals on novel technologies, methods of interacting with patients during home interventions, as well as provision of standardized guidelines for collecting data.

Thus, optimizing Living Lab methodologies, addressing technology use challenges, harmonizing devices and metrics, conducting larger-scale economic impact assessments and implementing patient-centered recommendations to advance transitional care practices further, should be the main focus of future researches and applications.

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